

Thematization Peculiarities and Prosodic Feature of British Limericks

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Abstract

The paper explores the functional thematization patterns in the British limerick poems. Simply put, the more unmarked theme in most frequent, the more basic in all the three types of thematic construction. The analysis of the data indicates that unmarked thematic prediction assigns to topical and textual limericks comparing them with the interpersonal. On the other side, masculine rhymes are higher in rates in these limericks than the feminine ones. Limericists use masculine rhyme to create specific sound patterns and to link lines as a means to help emphasize their theme. In general, both qualitative and quantitative data analysis were employed in this study. Qualitative analysis was carried out in order to identify and categorize marked thematization patterns and types of rhymes in this study. Quantitative analysis, on the other hand, was conducted to determine the occurrences of thematization patterns and markedness besides the two types of rhyme (masculine and feminine) in the British limericks under analysis.

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1. Introduction

Poetry can be viewed as a literary medium for recording , forming , controlling and communicating human experience. Most forms of poetry follow a specific format for words (rhyme and syllables) . Writing poetry/ limerick poems helps to gain confidence as one plays with the language and thinks creatively about specific topics . All poetry benefits from sensory words and a strong action verbs while faithful to the particular rules of the poetic form.

Hereof , Jonathan Dean (1947-50) wrote :

*The limerick is a fun five poem,
Enjoyed by all those that known 'em,
With two rhymes up top,
The one last to stop,
And two in between , not below'em .*

The present paper aims at identifying a suprasegmental (phonaesthetic device) and the functional aspects of clause formation in the British limericks . The paper identifies the phonic structure of rhyme words i.e., masculine and feminine to figure out whether these limericks display systematic alternation of **masculine** and **feminine rhyme** formation. It also aims at looking over the configuration of **theme-rheme** and especially **'Theme markedness'** in writing the limericks . In this respect , the researchers have gathered 30 British limericks under analysis from *The Penguin Book of Limericks* (1991) by Eric Oakley Parrott .

The paper tries to answer the following :

- 1-What are the theme types employed by British limericks writers?
- 2- Is markedness a focal point in the organization of the limericks?
- 3-What are the rhyme patterns employed by British Limericks writers?

2- English limerick: An Overview

The limerick is basically a story in five lines of verse . “There are usually nine beats in lines one , two , and five . There are six beats in lines three and four” . The ninth beats in lines one , two and five are accentuated ; and this is called ‘anapestic rhythm or foot’ (two short syllables followed by one long syllable) . Moreover , The first line forms the scene and explains the main character (Marsh , 1997:viii).

In this respect , Edward Lear is the outstanding example :

*There was a young person of Smyrna
Whose grandmother threatened to burn her,
But she seized on the cat,
and said Granny , burn that!*

You incongruous old woman of Smyrna!

“The first line of a limerick traditionally introduces a person and a place, with the place appearing at the end of the first line and therefore establishing the rhyme scheme for the second and fifth lines.” In early limericks, the last line was often basically a repeat of the first line. Despite that this is no longer customary (Jensen, 2008:65-66).

Sometimes a limericist begins a limerick by thinking what he wants to state. And by choosing a topic (e.g., a school friend) and then thinking what rhymes are available for that word. At the end, creating some sort of story out of them (Ibid.)

A limerick is five lines long with the rhyme scheme aabba.

This means that lines 1, 2 and 5 rhyme with each other, and lines 3 and 4 rhyme with each other. They also have a bouncing rhythm. Limericks are meant to be funny, and often employ elements of literature such as hyperbole, onomatopoeia and alliteration. The first line usually sets up the idea of the poem, and the last is generally the punch line (Jensen, 2008:65).

After Lear, most limericks followed suit: “they are generally composed of three metrical feet in the first, second, and fifth lines, with two metrical feet in the third and fourth, but deviations from the pattern can be diverting”, as in: (Weissmann, 2008:2603)

There was a young man from Japan

Whose limericks never would scan

When they said it was so

He replied, “Yes, I know,

*But I always try to get as many words into the last line as
ever I possibly can.”*

In Mary Cooper’s 1744 book, “Tommy Thumb’s Pretty Song Book”, the following poem in limerick form appears and is the first example in print of an illustrated limerick. Today, it remains well-known in different forms: (Jensen, 2008:64)

Hickere, Dickere Dock,

A Mouse ran up the Clock,

The Clock Struck One,

The Mouse fell down,

And Hickere Dickere Dock.

“The name limerick has its reference to the country or city in Ireland by the name of limerick. The limerick as a form of poetry appears in 1880 in a New Brunswick Newspaper. The name was documented in the New English Dictionary in 1898 in England in 1902. Edward Lear was the first who utilized the limerick in the 19th century in America (Parrott, 1983: 9-10).

In this respect, Edward Lear did not invent the limerick. On the other side, he may have played some part in popularizing the limerick form of poetry in his “Book of Nonsense”. The “Book of Nonsense” was first published in 1845 and then in 1872, it was termed as “Nonsense Verse” (Ibid.). The concluding line of the following limerick usually ended with the final word of the first line:

There once was an old man from Peru

His poor llamas came down with the flu

In the valley he passed

All the people who gasped

At the beast that was uttering “moo”

3- Theme and Rheme Formation:

The terms theme / rheme are first put by Mathesius (1939). He believes that theme is the part that comes first in a sentence and rheme is the next part.

“Theme/rheme plays a major role in organizing the message and in enabling it to be communicated and understood clearly (Halliday, 1994). On the other side, (Alonso, and McCabe, 1998) say that “whatever is chosen to be the first place, will influence the hearer/reader’s interpretation of everything that comes next in the discourse since it will constitute the initial textual context for everything that follows”.

Halliday (1994) also points out that each clause conveys a message that has two parts. What comes first is (the theme). What comes last is the (rheme). The theme usually constrains given information and the rheme, new information. “In the English language, the theme includes the lexical items (up to and including the first participant, process or circumstance) taking first position in the clause. These lexical items signal what the message will be about (White, 2000)”. According to Bloor and Bloor (1995), the concept theme in English is “the idea represented by the constituent at the starting of the clause.”

Fries (1983: 118) makes the point that "there are good and sufficient internal grammatical reasons to say that the beginning is special for some reason" and goes on to argue that "the initial position in the sentence, or sentence level Theme, means 'point of departure of the sentence as message'" (Ibid: 119). The first participant, process or circumstances are included in the theme as the beginning of the clause (White, 2000: 154).

The Theme is the starting point of a clause which includes the first Participant, Process or Circumstance (White, 2000: 154). Additionally, Halliday and Matthiessen (2004 cited in Thompson, 2004: 143) explain the Theme as "that which locates and orients the clause within its context." With regard to Fairclough (1994), the Theme is the text producer's point of departure in a clause. It corresponds to what is taken to be 'given' information i.e., that is information already known for text producers and interpreters.

The concept theme according to Brown and Yule (1983 : 133) is not only the starting point of the message. It also has a role of integrating to what has been said. They (Ibid.) believe that it is the left-most constituent of the sentence which has two important functions. The first function brings a coherent point of view. The second function serves as a point of departure for the further development of the discourse point for the message. Strauss and Corbin (1990 : 61) also state that the links between expressions and themes are "conceptual labels placed on discrete happenings, events, and other instances of phenomena". Themes, or categories, are the classification of more discrete concepts. "This classification is discovered when concepts are compared one against another and appear to pertain to a similar phenomenon. more abstract concepts are called a category". In accordance to Halliday (1985: 65) "theme has an important and basic role in the way discourse is organized. So, the concept theme is called 'context-dependent information'. Whereas, the concept rheme is 'new and context independent information'. Halliday and Matthiessen (2004: 65) suggest that "as a message structure, therefore, a clause consists of theme accompanied by a rheme; and the structure is expressed by the order- whatever is chosen as the theme is put first". Alice Davidson (1980) point out that "the more marked the construction, the more likely that an implicated meaning will be that which the utterance is intended to convey" (Cited in Brown & Yule, 1983). The following are the types of theme according to Halliday (2004:61-63):

3.1 Topical theme: "is the first experiential element of a clause, whether participant, circumstance or process. It's that simple any textual or interpersonal elements that precede the topical theme are also thematic" (Ibid.) .There is only one topical theme the normal reference to the source of the information. Examples are :

- 1-My uncle visited me last week.
 Topical theme rheme (unmarked)
- 2-last week , my uncle visited me.
 Topical theme rheme (marked)

In Hallidayan terms, there is an unmarked theme if the first ideational/ topical element is the subject. "If we first encounter any other ideational/topical element, theme stops at that element and becomes marked. To this point, the subject is not mentioned in the theme". Moreover, Matthiessen, adds that this type of subject has some thematic prominence. This is connected to the fact that it may relate to the method of development as it is unmarked theme of the sentence/ clause (1992: 51)

3.2 Textual theme: refers to the conjunctions like (and, but), relatives like (what, when) when they come at the beginning of the clause. See the following example:

- 3-But he does not understand me .
 Textual rheme

Intriguingly, Butt et al (1995: 135ff; 158) subjoin that the relative pronouns as well as adverbs and the prepositional phrases are also part of the textual theme because they introduce a foreground element to the sentence. Likewise, they cannot occupy the participant position.

Moreover, a sentence that starts with a verb, i.e. an infinite verb is classified as a textual theme since the unidentified verb form introduces a forefront unit to a sentence (Ibid.).

- 4- Spoke the boss to his clerk, don't be late again
Interpersonal theme rheme

3.3 Interpersonal theme: displays a point of view on the content of the remainder of the clause. It comes before the rheme indicating the relationship between participants in the text. It is usually represented by the interrogative case.

- 5-What tremendously easy questions you ask.
 Interpersonal theme rheme

4- Masculine and Feminine Rhymes:

Rhyme is an important phonological component of English verse. Rhyme is a repetition of some arrangement of vowels and consonants at the ends of lines, or sometimes in the middle, and is defined by H. W. Fowler in *Modern English Usage* as "identity of sounds between words or lines extending back from the end to the last fully accented vowel and not farther" (Boulton, 1982: .45). Stallworthy (2005: 2036) defines it as "the concurrence in two or more lines, of the last stressed

vowel of all speech sounds' and adds that 'it is closely associated with English poetry'. To Wales (2011: 371) it is "a kind of phonetic echo found in verse: more precisely, a phonemic matching". Two main types of rhyme can be distinguished as follows:

4.1-Masculine (or full) rhyme refers to the identity between the nucleus and coda of stressed monosyllabic words at the end of two or more lines of poetry, for example: *day/play/say*. This rhyme occurs frequently in iambic verse or as catalectic variations in trochaic verse (Boulton, 1982: 46; Stallworthy ,2005: 2037).

When the words are monosyllabic ('bear' and 'bare') , they are masculine , whereas , when the words are polysyllabic , they are feminine . Examples are ('horner' and 'corner') (Gill, 1995 : 390-391) .

In addition to knowing what masculine rhyme is, it's also helpful to understand why a poet might use it in a poem, or what masculine rhyme contributes to a poem. There are several ways to emphasize particular words in a poem. Placement in a line, stress, and rhyme all make words stand out. In many examples, all the masculine rhymes occur at the end of the line; just by having that white space to their right, these words are more prominent, more visible. Our eyes linger on those final words before we move onto the next line. Stress, too, emphasizes a word; words like to, the, an, a, and, if, or, at, etc., are usually all unstressed in poetic lines, while stressed words have more meaning, more life. And, when words are rhymed, they stand out (Ibid.) . The more times we hear a certain sound repeated, the more we pay attention to that sound. So, having masculine rhymes (especially those at the end of lines) help a poet to really emphasize the important words of a poem. Whether a reader realizes it or not, stressed syllables and words tend to stick in our memories better, as do the repetition of sounds that we find in rhyme (Wager, 2018).

4.2- Feminine rhyme often consists of two (or more) syllables in which a stressed syllable is followed by an unstressed syllable. For example: *Horner/corner, chiming/rhyming*. Feminine rhymes are common in trochaic verse, or as a variation (a hypermetric final foot) in iambic verse. Some feminine rhymes involve pairs in which a single word rhymes with a phrase thereby highlighting the unstressed words, for example: *pudding/mud in, intellectual/hen-pecked you all, persuaded/they did*. (Boulton, 1982: 46; Stallworthy ,2005: 2037).

The vast majority of English poems until the twentieth century have rhymes of one syllable, if they rhyme at all, blank verse (unrhymed iambic pentameter) having long been a favourite English form. In English poetry, feminine rhymes are less common, but in the poetry of some other languages (e.g., Italian) feminine rhymes are more common. Poets quite often use masculine and feminine rhymes in alternation; this generally seems to produce a very melodious verse. Swinburne, a poet of more music than meaning at times, particularly favours this kind of rhyme scheme:

From too much love of *living*,
From hope and fear set *free*,
We thank with brief *thanksgiving*
Whatever gods may *be*
That no life lives for *ever*;
That dead men rise up *never*;
That even the weariest *river*
Winds somewhere safe to *sea*.

The Garden of Proserpine

Feminine rhymes are often used in humorous verse, in which they please by their witty ingenuity. The delight here is probably almost entirely in the pleasant shock of the unexpected (Boulton, 1982: 49-50).

5- Data Analysis:

The followings are the limericks to be analysed in terms of thematization patterns / markedness and rhyme formation . Model of the analysis related to thematization and markedness is basically an eclectic one from Halliday and Matthiessen (2004) and Butt et al., (1995). For the prosodic feature , Arp and Johnson (2009: 1664) is brought forth as a model of analysis.

There was a toddler named **Charlee** (poly/feminine)
Whose dad liked to watch Guthrie and **Farley**
She"d squeal , clap and **giggle**, (Mono/ Masculine)
Walk and crawl with a **wiggle**,
As her grandma rides up on a **Harely** (poly/feminine)

By **Val Kolle**

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
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Topical	She	unmarked	'd squeal , clap and <i>giggle</i> , Walk and crawl with a wiggle,
	her grandma	marked	rides up on a Harely
Textual	There	unmarked	was a toddler named Charlee
	Whose dad	unmarked	liked to watch Guthrie and Farley
	As	marked	rides up on a Harely
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

There was an old lady of **France**, (Mono/ Masculine)
 Who taught little ducklings to **dance**;
 When she said, "*Tick-a-Tack*"! (Mono/ Masculine)
 They only said "*Quack*"!
 Which grieved that old lady of **France**(Mono/ Masculine)

By Michael R. Burch

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	She	marked	said, " <i>Tick-a-Tack</i> "!
	They	unmarked	only said " <i>Quack</i> "
Textual	There	unmarked	was an old lady of France
	Who	unmarked	taught little ducklings to dance;
	When	marked	said, " <i>Tick-a-Tack</i> "!
	Which	unmarked	grieved that old lady of France
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

There was an old Man in a **tree** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Who was horribly bored by a **Bee**;
 When they said "Does it *buzz*?" (Mono/ Masculine)
 He replied, "yes it **does**"
 It's a regular brute of a **Bee!** (Mono/ Masculine)

By Ogden Nash

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical Unmarked	They	marked	said "Does it <i>buzz</i> "
	He	unmarked	replied, "yes it does"
	It	unmarked	"s a regular brute of a Bee!
Textual	There	unmarked	was an old Man in a tree
	Who	unmarked	

	When	marked	was horribly bored by a Bee; said "Does it <i>buzz</i> "
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

There was an old man who could *piss* ((Mono/ Masculine)
Through a ring – and what's more , nervous *miss* (Mono/ Masculine)
People came by the *score* (Mono/ Masculine)
And bellowed: "Encore"!
Won't you do it again , Sir? Bis! Bis! *Bis!* (Mono/ Masculine)
By Norman Douglas

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	People	unmarked	came by the score
Textual	There	unmarked	was an old man who could <i>piss</i> and what's more , nervous <i>miss</i> bellowed: "Encore"
	Through a ring	marked	
	And	unmarked	
Interpersonal	Won't you	unmarked	do it again , Sir? Bis! Bis!

A sailor boy named Happy *Jack* (Mono/ Masculine)
At school did his cranium *crack*
To elevate *pupils* (poly/ Feminine)
And having few *scruples*
He wickedly tried a new *track!* (Mono/ Masculine)
By Eleanor Maclean

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A sailor boy He	unmarked unmarked	named Happy Jack tried a new track
Textual	At school	unmarked	did his cranium <i>crack</i> To elevate pupils having few scruples tried a new track!
	And wickedly	unmarked marked	
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

A combustible woman from *Thang* (Mono/ Masculine)
Exploded one day with a *bang*
The maid then rushed *in* (Mono/ Masculine)
And said with a *grin*
Pardon me , madam – you *rang?* (Mono/ Masculine)
By Lewis Carroll

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A combustible woman from Thang	unmarked	Exploded one day with a <i>bang</i>
	The maid	unmarked	rushed in
Textual	Then	unmarked	rushed in
	And	marked	said with a grin
Interpersonal	Pardon me , madam	unmarked	you rang

What a limerick is a *crunch* (Mono/ Masculine)
Is a bit like a loonly's light *lunch* (Mono/ Masculine)

Though it briefly delights

It's just four nutty **bites** (mono/ Masculine)

Swallowed down with a ludicrous **punch** (Mono/ Masculine)

By Robert Louis

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	a limerick	marked	is a <i>crunch</i>
	It	unmarked	s just four nutty bites
Textual	What	marked	is a <i>crunch</i>
	Though	marked	briefly delights
Interpersonal	Is	unmarked	a bit like a loonly's light lunch

An ambitious young fellow named **Matt** (Mono/ Masculine)

Tried to parachute using his **hat**

Folks below looked so **small** (Mono/ Masculine)

As he started to **fall**,

Then got bigger and bigger and **splat!** (Mono/ Masculine)

By Ogden Nash

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	An ambitious young fellow	unmarked	named Matt Tried to parachute using his hat
	Folks	unmarked	looked so small
	he	marked	started to fall
Textual	Below	unmarked	looked so small
	As	marked	started to fall
	Then	unmarked	got bigger and bigger and <i>splat!</i>
Interpersonal	-----		-----

A native of Chalama **zug** (Mono/ Masculine)

Once fell overboard from a **tug**.

He cried, "Ding-dong **boller** (poly/ feminine)

Doo jango zong **zoller**,"

Which means "*Glug-glug glug glug-glug glug*." (Mono/ Masculine)

By Robert Louis

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A native of Chalamazug	unmarked	fell overboard from a tug.
	He	unmarked	cried, "Ding-dong boller Doo jango zong zoller,"
Textual	Once	unmarked	fell overboard from a tug.
	Which	unmarked	means " <i>Glug-glug glug glug-glug glug</i> "
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

A mouse in her room woke Miss **Dowd** (Mono/ Masculine)
 She was frightened, it must be **allowed**, (poly/feminine)
 Soon a happy thought hit **her** (Mono/ Masculine)
 To scare off the **critter** (poly/feminine)
 She sat up in bed and **meowed** (Mono/ Masculine)

By H. G. Wells

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A mouse She It a happy thought She	Unmarked Unmarked Unmarked Marked unmarked	woke Miss Dowd was frightened must be allowed hit her To scare off the critter sat up in bed and <i>meowed</i>
Textual	in her room Soon	Unmarked marked	woke Miss Dowd hit her
Interpersonal	-----		-----

A tutor who tooted a **flute** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Tried to teach two young tooters to **toot** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Said the two to the tutor, "
 Is it harder to toot, **or . . .** (Mono/ Masculine)
 To tutor two tooters to **toot?**" (Mono/ Masculine)

By Carolyn Wells

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A tutor	unmarked	tooted a flute Tried to teach two young tooters to toot
Textual	who	unmarked	tooted a flute Tried to teach two young tooters to toot
Interpersonal	Said Is	Marked unmarked	the two to the tutor it harder to toot, or . . . To tutor two tooters to <i>toot</i>

There was an old man from **Crewe** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Who wanted to know how to **moo**.
 He studied a **cow** (Mono/ Masculine)
 To try and learn **how**
 But all he could do was **boo**. (Mono/ Masculine)

By Michael Rosen

Type of the theme		Unmarked/Marked	Rheme
Topical	He he	unmarked marked	studied a cow To try and learn how could do was <i>boo</i> .
Textual	There Who But all	unmarked unmarked marked	was an old man from Crewe wanted to know how to <i>moo</i>

			could do was <i>boo</i> .
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

A bespectacled artist called **Lear** (Mono/ Masculine)
 First perfected this smile in a *sneer*
 He was clever and **witty**; (poly/feminine)
 He gave life to this **ditty** –
 That original author called **Lear** (Mono/ Masculine)

By Erica Jong

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A bespectacled artist He He	unmarked unmarked unmarked	called Lear was clever and witty gave life to this ditty
Textual	First That original author	unmarked marked	perfected this smile in a <i>sneer</i> That original author called
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

Dennis's basketball **gang** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Are all in the way to **Pyongyang** ,
 To take on some **short** , (Mono/ Masculine)
 Left wing people in **sport** ,
 The odds are they'll win with a **bang** (Mono/ Masculine)

By John Maynes

Type of the theme		Marked/unmarked	Rheme
Topical	Dennis's basketball gang The odds	unmarked unmarked	Are all in the way to Pyongyang , , are they'll win with a <i>bang</i>
Textual	To take on some short	unmarked	Left wing people in sport
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

The bottle of perfume that Willie **sent** (Mono/ Masculine)
 Was highly displeasing to **Millicent** (poly/ feminine)
 Her thanks were so **cold** (Mono/ Masculine)
 They quarreled , I am **told**
 Through that silly scent Willie sent **Millicent**(poly/feminine)

By W.H. Auden

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	The bottle of perfume that Willie sent Her thanks They Willie	unmarked unmarked unmarked marked	Was highly displeasing to Millicent were so cold quarreled , I am told sent Millicent
Textual	Through that silly scent	marked	sent Millicent
Interpersonal	-----		-----

A crossword compiler named **Moss** (Mono/ Masculine)

Who found himself quite a **loss**

When asked „why so **blue**“? (Mono/ Masculine)

Said „I haven“t a **clue**

I am 2 down to put 1 across“

By Lewis Faye Copeland

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A crossword compiler	unmarked	named Moss
	I	unmarked	am 2 down to put 1 across
Textual	Who	unmarked	found himself quite a loss
	When	unmarked	asked „why so blue
Interpersonal	Said	marked	I haven“t a clue

There was a young fellow named **Hall** (Mono/ Masculine)

Who died in the spring in the **fall**

Twould have been a bad **thing** (Mono/ Masculine)

Had he died in the **spring**

But he didn“t – he died in the **fall** (Mono/ Masculine)

By Jerry Merchant

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	T	unmarked	would have been a bad thing
	he	marked	didn“t – he died in the fall
Textual	There	unmarked	was a young fellow named Hall
	Who	unmarked	died in the spring in the fall
	But	marked	didn“t – he died in the fall
Interpersonal	Had	unmarked	he died in the spring

The youth who frequent picture **palaces** (poly/feminine)

Have no need for psycho**analysis** (poly/feminine)

And thought Dr. Freud

Is distinctly **annoyed** (poly/feminine)

They cling to their long –lasting **fallacies** (poly/feminine)

By James Dunn

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	the youth who frequent picture palaces	unmarked	Have no need for psychoanalysis
	They	unmarked	cling to their long – lasting fallacies
Textual	And distinctly	unmarked marked	thought Dr. Freud annoyed
Interpersonal	Is	unmarked	annoyed

There was a fair maid who would **sigh** (Mono/ Masculine)

“Ah, love, is a tourture ! she’d **cry** (Mono/ Masculine)

Said her Pa “Tommyrot!”

Tisn’t love that you’ve **got** (Mono/ Masculine)

Tis a mixture – pork , pudding” and **pie**” (Mono/ Masculine)

By Stanton Vaughn

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	Love	marked	, is a tourture
	She	marked	d cry
	T	unmarked	isn’t love that you’ve got
	T	unmarked	is a mixture – pork , pudding” and pie”
Textual	There	unmarked	was a fair maid who would sigh
	Ah	marked	, is a tourture.
Interpersonal	Said	marked	her Pa “Tommyrot

A girl who was quite an adept

As to Reginald’s elbow she **crept** (Mono/ Masculine)

Whispered into his **ear** , (Mono/ Masculine)

“This is leap year , my **dear**;

Don’t you think you could leap? – And he “**leapt**” (Mono/ Masculine)

By Dixon Merritt

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A girl	Unmarked	was quite an adept
	She	Marked	crept <i>Whispered</i> into his ear
	he	marked	leapt
Textual	Who	marked	was quite an adept
	As to Reginald’s elbow	marked	crept <i>Whispered</i> into his ear
	“This And	unmarked marked	is leap year , my dear leapt
Interpersonal	Don’t	unmarked	you think you could leap

There was once a poet named **Immerick**, (poly/feminine)

Who worked forty days on a "**limerick**,"

At the end of which **time**. (Mono/ Masculine)

He remarked of his **rhyme**,

"There's a limp in the limb of my **limerick**.")poly/feminine)

By John Updike

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	He	unmarked	remarked of his rhyme

Textual	There	unmarked	was once a poet named Immerick worked forty days on a "limerick remarked of his rhyme 's a limp in the limb of my limerick
	Who	unmarked	
	At the end of which time	marked	
	There	unmarked	
Interpersonal	-----		-----

There once was a young man who **said** ; (Mono/ Masculine)

I Have always been **bored**

when I've read Poems **Byronic** (poly/feminine)

So I find it **ironic**,

When limericks pour from my **head**". (Mono/ Masculine)

By Richard C. Long

Type of the theme		Marked/unmarked	Rheme
Topical	I	unmarked	Have always been bored when I've read Poems Byronic find it ironic pour from my head
	I	marked	
	limericks	marked	
Textual	There	marked	was a young man who said
	Once	unmarked	was a young man who said
	So	marked	find it ironic
	When	marked	pour from my head
Interpersonal	-----		-----

A canner exceedingly can **canny** (poly/feminine)

One morning remarked to his **granny**

“ A canner can **can** (Mono/ Masculine)

Any thing that he **can**

But a canner can“t can a can , can **he**?” (Mono/ Masculine)

By Carolyn Wells

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	A canner	unmarked	can canny
	A canner	unmarked	can can Any thing that he can
	a canner	marked	can“t can a can
Textual	Exceedingly	Marked	can canny remarked to his granny can“t can a can
	One morning	Unmarked	
	But	marked	
Interpersonal	Can	unmarked	he

*There was a young lady of **station**(poly/feminine)*

*I love man was her sole **exclamation**;*

*But when men cried: 'you **flatter**',*

*She replied,'Oh!no **matter***

Isle of Man is the true **explanation**.

By Lewis Carroll

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>I</i>	unmarked	<i>love man was her sole exclamation</i>
	<i>men</i>	marked	<i>cried: 'you flatter'</i>
	<i>she</i>	unmarked	<i>replied, 'Oh!no matter</i>
	<i>Isle of Man</i>	marked	<i>is the true explanation</i>
Textual	<i>There</i>	unmarked	<i>was a young lady of station</i>
	<i>But</i>	marked	<i>cried: 'you flatter'</i>
	<i>when</i>	marked	<i>cried: 'you flatter'</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	

*There was a young person of **Smyrna** (poly/feminine)*
*Whose grandmother threatened to burn **her**, (mono/masculine)*
*But she seized on the **cat**, (mono/masculine)*
*and said Granny , burn **that!** (mono/masculine)*
*You incongruous old woman of **Smyrna!** (poly/feminine)*

By Edward Lear

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>she</i>	unmarked	<i>seized on the cat</i>
Textual	<i>There</i>	unmarked	<i>was a young person of Smyrna</i>
	<i>Whose grandmother</i>	unmarked	<i>threatened to burn her</i>
	<i>But</i>	marked	<i>seized on the cat</i>
	<i>and</i>	marked	<i>Granny , burn that! You incongruous old woman of Smyrna</i>
Interpersonal	<i>said</i>	marked	<i>Granny , burn that! You incongruous old woman of Smyrna</i>

*There once was an old man from **Peru** (poly/feminine)*
*His poor llamas came down with the **flu** , (mono/masculine)*
*In the valley he **passed** (poly/feminine)*
*All the people who **gasp** (poly/feminine)*
*At the beast that was uttering "**moo**" , (mono/masculine)*

By Lewis Carroll

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>All the people</i>	unmarked	<i>gasp</i>
Textual	<i>There</i>	Marked	<i>an old man from Peru</i>

	Once	unmarked	<i>an old man from Peru</i>
	<i>His poor llamas</i>	unmarked	<i>came down with the flu In the valley he passed</i>
	Who	marked	<i>gasp</i>
	<i>At the beast that</i>	marked unmarked	<i>was uttering "moo was uttering "moo</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

*There was a young man from Japan
Whose limericks never would scan (mono/masculine)
When they said it was so
He replied, "Yes, I know,
But I always try to get as many words into the last line as ever I possibly can*

By Rudyard Kipling

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>They</i>	marked	<i>said it was so</i>
	<i>He</i>	unmarked	<i>replied, "Yes, I know</i>
	<i>I</i>	marked	<i>try to get as many words into the last line as ever I possibly can</i>
Textual	<i>There</i>	unmarked	<i>was a young man from Japan</i>
	<i>Whose limericks</i>	marked	<i>would scan</i>
	<i>Never</i>		<i>would scan</i>
	<i>When</i>	unmarked	<i>said it was so</i>
	<i>But</i>	marked	<i>try to get as many words into the last line as ever I possibly can</i>
		marked	<i>try to get as many words into the last line as ever I possibly can</i>
	<i>always</i>	unmarked	<i>try to get as many words into the last line as ever I possibly can</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

*Hickere, Dickere Dock, (mono/masculine)
A Mouse ran up the Clock,
The Clock Struck One,
The Mouse fell down,
And Hickere Dickere Dock.*

By Eleanor Maclean

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>Hickere, Dickere A Mouse The Clock</i>	unmarked unmarked unmarked	<i>Dock, ran up the Clock, Struck One</i>

	<i>The Mouse Hickere Dickere</i>	unmarked marked	<i>fell down, Dock.</i>
Textual	<i>And</i>	marked	<i>Dock.</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

A dragon flies through the night sky (mono/masculine)

Not to be seen by a mortals eye

They fly so high not to be seen

Whoever can see one has eyes that are keen

People try to see them in the great night

By Lewis Carroll

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>A dragon</i>	Unmarked	<i>flies through the night sky</i>
	<i>They</i>	Unmarked	<i>fly so high not to be seen</i>
	<i>People</i>	unmarked	<i>try to see them in the great night</i>
Textual	<i>Not to</i>	unmarked	<i>be seen by a mortals eye</i>
	<i>whoever</i>	unmarked	<i>can see one has eyes that are keen</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

There was a small boy of *Quebec* (poly/feminine)

Who was buried in snow to his *neck*(mono/masculine)

When they said 'Are you *friz*?'

He replied, yes, I *is*-

But we don't call this cold in *Quebec*. (poly/feminine)

By Stanton Vaughn

Type of the theme		Marked/Unmarked	Rheme
Topical	<i>They</i>	marked	<i>said 'Are you friz?'</i>
	<i>He</i>	unmarked	<i>replied, yes, I is- don't call this cold in Quebec</i>
	<i>we</i>	marked	
Textual	<i>There</i>	unmarked	<i>was a small boy of Quebec</i>
	<i>Who</i>	unmarked	<i>was buried in snow to his neck</i>
	<i>When</i> <i>But</i>	marked marked	<i>said 'Are you friz?'</i> <i>don't call this cold in Quebec</i>
Interpersonal	-----	-----	-----

6- Methodology

6.1 Materials

The researchers have gathered 30 British limericks under analysis from *The Penguin Book of Limericks* (1991) by Eric Oakley Parrott. These limericks are analyzed in terms of thematization structure / marked and unmarked. For the prosodic feature, rhyme patterns are investigated in order to show the matter of occurrences of masculine/ feminine in these selected limericks.

7- Results and Discussion:

7.1 Results:

From the analysis of the 30 limericks, results show that the most dominant theme is textual. Textual theme records 83 occurrences from the total number 171 with a rate of 48.539%. The second occurrence of the theme is topical that it occupies 76 occurrences from the number of 171 and it records 44.444%, whereas interpersonal is the least type of the theme which occurs in the British limericks and records 12 only with a percentage of 7.017%. Simply, there is no outstanding differences between topical and textual themes distribution in the analysis. And comparing the interpersonal theme with textual and topical came about evidence. Generally, if a textual theme occurs thematically, it may not exhaust the thematic potential of the clause and it is, thus, considered to be one part of the theme in the clause. See table (1) below.

Table (1) The Occurrences and the Percentages of the Thematization Patterns in the Limericks

Types of theme	Occurrence	%
textual	83	48.539
topical	76	44.444
interpersonal	12	7.017
total	171	100

2- Theme prediction is categorized by being unmarked as it records 107 instances and indicates 53 instances for topical theme with a rate of 49.532%; textual theme indicates 46 instances and assigns 42.990%, and the last one is interpersonal which records 8 instances and assigns 7.476%. On the other hand markedness shows less frequent indication in the thematic prediction of British limericks under analysis: the total number of marked themes is 64 and it records 23 instances in topical theme with a rate of 35.937%, textual theme indicates 37 instances with a rate of 57.812%, whereas interpersonal shows a very low distribution of markedness with a rate of 6.25%. The following table summarizes marked and unmarked themes distributions:

Table (2) The Distributions of the Markedness of the Themes in the Limericks

Types of theme	Marked	%	Unmarked	%
textual	37	57.812%	46	42.992%
topical	23	35.938%	53	49.532%
interpersonal	4	6.25%	8	7.476%
total	64	100	107	100

3- The total number of masculine and feminine rhymes is 147. The occurrence of masculine rhymes in the limericks is 109 with a rate of 74.149%, whereas the feminine rhyme indicates 38 instances with a rate of 25.851% as follows:

Table (3) Types of Rhyme in the Limericks

Types of rhyme	occurrence	%
masculine	109	74.149
feminine	38	25.851
total	147	100

7.2 Conclusion:

- 1- Results show that to tie the sequences of the limericks events together, to enhance the argument, and to make effective flow of lexical chain, textual themes are mainly utilized as they record high frequencies in these British limericks. In general, it seems that these textual themes are used to organize other experiential and interpersonal themes into and coherent whole. It (textual theme) is an impressive channel of limerical expression.
- 2- It is concluded that the analysis of the limericks is approximately similar in their identification of textual and topical thematization. i.e., (there is no significant variation between textual and topical theme realization).
- 3- Generally, once you have identified the topical theme in a clause, it is possible to consign all the remaining clause constituents to the rheme role.
- 4- Unmarked themes are used more and Marked ones show less usage; which means that the structure transposition for emphasis occurred less that shows according to textual thematization than the topical ones. In this respect, markedness means that the occurrence of some phenomenon is less typical or frequent. Hence, a theme is marked, is less typical or frequent for it to be realised that way i.e., the opposite is correct in accordance to the unmarked themes.

- 5- Limerical perspectives indicate high frequencies in the occurrences of masculine rhymes than the feminine ones. So, having masculine rhymes (especially those at the end of lines) help a limerick writer to really emphasize the important words of a poem. Whether a reader realizes it or not, stressed syllables and words tend to stick in the memories of the readers better, as do the repetition of sounds that one may find in rhyme.

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